

Management Analysis of Facilities and Infrastructure for The Implementation of The 19th Student Sports Week in The Pencak Silat Sport Branch

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study is to measure the achievement and standardization of pencak silat competitions reviewed from the management of infrastructure facilities. The measurement process is carried out by observation method. The purpose of the direct observation is to provide an overview of how the standardization of the XIX National Student Sports Week match for pencak silat sports is reviewed from the management of facilities and infrastructure.

This research was conducted at the University of Muhammadiyah Surakarta, which hosted the Pencak Silat competition of the 19th National Student Sports Week. This type of research is qualitative research. The sampling technique used is purposive sampling, with the following sample criteria: Chief Executive of Pencak Silat Sport, Coordinator of Match Fields, Coordinator of Infrastructure and 10 POMNAS Athletes who won the best medals from the contingents of DKI Jakarta, Central Java, East Java, West Java, and the Special Region of Yogyakarta. Data collection techniques include interviews, non-participatory observations, and documentation. This study uses descriptive qualitative analysis techniques for data analysis.

The findings of the study include a strong legal foundation and goals for the 19th National Pencak Silat Sports Week. The structure of the committee consists of various parties and involves stakeholders. The event received support in the form of a complete and representative venue and infrastructure from the University of Muhammadiyah Surakarta. The budget is very limited. The funds allocated are sufficient to cover the honorarium for the technical committee. During the competition, standard operating procedures (SOPs) are applied, but one of the rules of the competition is modified. This competition produced pencak silat champions, who are projected to be sent by the country to compete in the ASEAN University Games, as a follow-up to the national competition. This study concluded that this pencak silat event was well organized. This research provides recommendations to policymakers, which can be useful for the planning of other national sports championships, including optimizing and prioritizing budget management and optimizing promotion and branding through various media platforms.

KEYWORDS: Management, Analysis, National Student Sports Week, Pencak Silat

I. INTRODUCTION

A sports match standard is a set of rules, rules, and guidelines used to ensure that a competition takes place in a fair, safe, and well-organized manner. This standard covers various aspects, including the rules of the game, the match system, refereeing, the eligibility of athletes, and the completeness of the facilities and infrastructure used during the match. The application of good standards will create professional competition, uphold sportsmanship, and minimize the risk of injury to athletes.

In the context of a national-scale sports event, such as the National Student Sports Week (POMNAS), the standard of the match is very important because it involves many participants from various regions. Therefore, the organization of the match must refer to the regulations set by the parent organization of the respective sports branches, both at the national and international levels. This aims to maintain uniformity of rules and the quality of the match.

The availability of facilities and infrastructure that meet standards greatly affects the quality of the match. Adequate facilities will support athlete performance, increase the objectivity of assessments, and ensure safety during competitions. On the other hand, facilities that do not meet standards may pose a risk of injury and reduce the quality of competition.

In the context of organizing events such as POMNAS, the standard of facilities and infrastructure is an important indicator in the evaluation of sports event management. Therefore, the organizers must ensure that all facilities and infrastructure needs are in accordance with applicable regulations so that the match can run optimally, professionally, and safely.

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One of the efforts to complement the self-development and competence of students in order to become graduates who have comprehensive intelligence and competitiveness is to be able to contribute to carrying out various activities, especially competitions in the field of sports, namely the National Student Sports Week (POMNAS). POMNAS is also one of the efforts in developing athlete coaching among students, namely by holding a multi-sports event for students on a national scale. The National Student Sports Week (POMNAS) is a national-level (inter-provincial) sports competition for university students for Diploma and Undergraduate study levels in Indonesia which is held every two years by the Student Sports Supervisory Board (BAPOMI) (PUSPRESNAS, 2023). POMNAS is also a sports competition event involving students from various universities in Indonesia. The POMNAS Championship provides an opportunity for athletes with student status to compete in various multievent sports.

Figure 1. Graphic Info of the Host of POMNAS 5 Last Edition

Sumber: Dokumentasi rapat bersama BAPOMI dan FORKOMAWA Jateng, 2025.

Based on the data from the documentation above, it can be concluded that Central Java Province is set to host POMNAS for the first time in 2025. The implementation of POMNAS in 2025 in Central Java Province will be carried out in several venues and cities. The cities that will be used as the organizer of the implementation of POMNAS are the cities of Semarang and Solo. The following will be presented Table 2 of the list of venues for the implementation of POMNAS in 2025 in the cities of Semarang and Solo:

Table 1. List of Venues for the Implementation of POMNAS XIX in 2025

No	Cabor	Venue	No	Cabor	Venue
1	Wushu	Auditorium Prof. Wuryanto UNNES	11	Pencak Silat	Edutorium KH. Ahmad Dahlan UMS
2	Panahan	Lapangan Prof. Dumadi UNNES	12	Taekwondo	Satria Sport Center UDINUS
3	Tenis Lapangan	Lapangan Tennis Dr. M. Sajoto UNNES	13	Atletik	GOR Tri Lomba Juang
4	Bulu Tangkis	GOR Badminton UNDIP	14	Renang	Kolam Renang GOR Jatidiri
5	Bola Basket	GOR Basket Prof. Susilo Wibowo UNDIP	15	Bola Voli Pasir	Lapangan Voli Pasir GOR Jatidiri
6	Karate	Lapangan Futsal Stadion UNDIP	16	Panjat Tebing	Panjat Tebing GOR Jatidiri
7	Tarung Derajat	GOR FKOR UNS	17	Bola Voli Indoor	Voli Indoor GOR Jatidiri
8	Sepak Takraw	GOR Kentingan UNS			
9	Petanque	Lapangan Petanque UNS			
10	Catur	Balairung UPGRIS Semarang			
			No	Ekshibisi	Venue
			1	Sepatu Roda	Velodrome Sepatu Roda GOR Jatidiri
			2	Pickelball	Lapangan Pickleball UNNES
			3	Woodball	Lapangan Prof. Dumadi UNNES

Sumber: Dokumentasi Raker BAPOMI dan FORKOMAWA Jateng, 2025.

Based on the data that has been presented, it can be concluded that BAPOMI Central Java Province has only been designated as the host of POMNAS for the first time which will take place in September 2025 centered in the cities of Semarang and the cities of Solo. The determination of match venues is in cooperation and involves higher education institutions, in this case sports venues and facilities owned by universities. In the implementation of sports events, all matches must meet the management standards for the implementation of sports events. Sports management is a process to organize all activities to achieve certain group goals

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with the functions of planning, organizing, directing, leading, supervising and evaluating related to sports or physical activities (Kusuma & Farida, 2021).

Based on the above opinion for the success and smooth running of the POMNAS XIX agenda which will take place in 2025, good management is needed in an institution. One of the important things in sports management is a comprehensive and scientific evaluation. Evaluation needs to be carried out in an organization, both sports organizations, and sports event organizing organizations. The determination of Central Java Province to host POMNAS in 2025, evaluation is very necessary to measure achievement and success. Management of the implementation of POMNAS XIX in 2025 for each sport contested.

Sports is one of the educational media that is able to provide benefits for students to develop the values needed in life as future leaders. Competitive sports activities will be beneficial for students for the development of character personalities that contain the values of intelligence, skills, emotional control, discipline, sportsmanship, democracy, unity and unity, and peace (Liu et al., 2022). Sports achievements for students are important things that must be achieved because students have two advantages, namely; First, the golden age of students to be able to achieve optimally in various fields, and second, students have high reasoning power, so they are able to solve problems quickly and accurately, so students need to emphasize aspects of selfdevelopment through sports (Priambudi & Warni, 2024).

II. METHODS

This research uses a qualitative research approach. This research approach was chosen to assess and examine the implementation of the XIX POMNAS in the pencak silat sports branch. This study uses non-participatory interview and observation techniques

According to (Falaahudin & Sugiyanto, 2013) Observation is one of the methods that can be used to obtain information about the focus of research. The focus of observation can be in the form of events, behaviors and expressions of people in the setting in which the researcher is located. In this method, the researcher needs sensitivity to the situation or setting where the observation is made (Norman & Creswell, 2010, p.156). In this study, the implementation of the XIX POMNAS in the pencak silat sports branch.

According to (Falaahudin & Sugiyanto, 2013) An interview is a conversation with a specific purpose. The conversation is carried out by two parties, namely the interviewer who asks the question and the interviewees who give the answer to the question (Moleong, 2010, p.186), while Sukarjo (2006, p.22) defines wa- wawancara as a type of data collection and recording of information, and or information that is carried out through conversations and questions and answers, either directly or indirectly with the data source.

A. Data, Instruments, and Data Collection Techniques

Data analysis techniques can be carried out with a qualitative analysis model where the essence is to analyze the interaction between research components and the data collection process during the research process. The data analysis technique used in qualitative descriptive analysis has 4 (four) stages of the latest interactive model from Miles et al., (2015), namely data collection, data condensation, data display, and the last step is conclusion drawing and verification.

Data condensation refers to the process of selecting, focusing, simplifying, abstracting, and transforming data contained in field records and transcripts in this study described as follows: 1) Selecting. According to Miles et al., (2015), researchers must act selectively, i.e. determine which dimensions are more important, which relationships may be more meaningful, and as a consequence, what information can be collected and analyzed. 2) Focusing. Miles et al., (2015) stated that focusing data is a form of pre-analysis. At this stage, the researcher focuses on data related to the formulation of the research problem. This stage is a continuation of the data selection stage. Researchers only limited data based on problem formulations.

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The stage of making a summary of the core, process, and statements that need to be maintained, so that they remain in it. At this stage, the data that has been collected is evaluated, especially related to the quality and adequacy of data. 4) Simplification and Transformation (data simplifying and transforming). The data in this study is further simplified and transformed in various ways, namely through strict selection through summaries or brief descriptions, classifying the data in a broader pattern, and so on.

Data presentation is an effort by which the researcher compiles and collects information in a matrix or configuration that is easy to understand. This kind of configuration will make it easier to draw conclusions or simplify complex information into an understandable form (Miles & Huberman, 2016). Simple and easy-to-understand data presentation is the main way to analyze valid qualitative descriptive data. The way to present this data is by presenting interview results data on the organizers of the 2025 National Student Sports Week for pencak silat sports and prospective pencak silat athletes who have participated in the 2025 National Student Sports Week in the form of interview excerpts accompanied by the name or code or initials of the informant, then the day, date, month, and year of the interview, and interview time is conducted.

Data Collection. Data collection from the methods carried out are observation, interviews and documentation. All of these types of data have one key aspect in general, the analysis of which mainly depends on the integrative and interpretive skills of the researcher. Interpretation is necessary because the data collected is rarely numerical, data rich in detail and long.

B. Data Collection Techniques

Data collection from the methods carried out are observation, interviews and documentation. All of these types of data have one key aspect in general, the analysis of which mainly depends on the integrative and interpretive skills of the researcher. Interpretation is necessary because the data collected is rarely numerical, data rich in detail and long.

Draw conclusions/verifications. Starting from the beginning of data collection, the researcher began to look for the meaning of the interview data on the evaluation of the management of the implementation of the XIX Student Sports Week (POMNAS) of the Pencak Silat sports branch. Next, the researcher searches for the meaning and explanation and then arranges certain relationship patterns into a unit that is easy to understand and interpret (Miles & Huberman, 2016).

III. RESULT

a. Planning of Facilities and Infrastructure

The informant said that planning facilities and infrastructure had been carried out since the initial stage of preparation for POMNAS XIX. The needs of facilities such as match courts, match mats, athletes' rooms, official rooms, medical rooms, and match support equipment are arranged based on the applicable pencak silat match standards. However, some informants mentioned that the preparation time was relatively short so that the planning was not fully mature.

b. Availability and Feasibility of Facilities

Most of the informants assessed that the main facilities such as the match arena, mats, sound system, scoreboard, and warming room were available and could be used properly. However, several limitations were found, including the limited number of athletes' dressing rooms, less than spacious warming areas, and supporting facilities such as toilets and official restrooms that were not fully adequate.

c. Management and Distribution of Facilities

The results of the interviews show that the management of facilities and infrastructure is carried out by a special team under the coordinator of facilities and infrastructure. The distribution of equipment to the match area is considered quite orderly, but in the early days of the match there was a delay in the provision of several equipment, such as light medical equipment and arena cleaning equipment.

d. Facility Maintenance and Security

The informant stated that the maintenance of facilities during the implementation of the activity was carried out periodically, especially in the cleanliness of mats and match arenas. Security and hygiene officers have been alerted, although the number of personnel is still considered less than optimal during the busy match schedule. This has an impact on handling delays when minor damage to the facility occurs.

e. Obstacles and Improvement Efforts

Some of the main obstacles revealed by the informants include budget limitations, space limitations, and coordination between committees that are not optimal at the beginning of the activity. As an effort to improve, the committee made technical adjustments in the field, added cleaning and technical personnel, and carried out intensive coordination between fields during the implementation of the activity.

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Observation was carried out directly during the implementation of the pencak silat match at POMNAS XIX, focusing on the condition of facilities and infrastructure at the activity site. The results of the observation showed the following findings:

a. Match Arena Condition

The pencak silat match arena at the XIX National Student Sports Week (POMNAS) was held in a sports building with relatively good, clean, and suitable conditions for use. In general, the main facilities of the match have met the basic standards for the implementation of pencak silat sports, both in terms of feasibility and safety.

The arrangement of the match court has been adjusted to the standard of pencak silat matches, where the match area uses a mat with a thickness of ± 5 cm which serves to reduce the risk of athlete injury. In addition, the size and boundaries of the competition arena have been clearly marked according to applicable regulations, thus supporting the smooth running of the match.

However, based on the results of observations on the field, the distance between the match arena and the spectator stands is quite close. This condition causes limited movement space for officials, especially referees, judges, and committees, especially when the match takes place with a large number of spectators. This has the potential to interfere with the mobility of officers and can affect comfort and safety during the match.

Figure 1 POMNAS Venue / Digital Scoring

b. Availability of Supporting Facilities

Supporting facilities for the implementation of pencak silat matches in the XIX National Student Sports Week (POMNAS) include athletes' warm-up rooms, medical rooms, official rooms, and media rooms. In general, these facilities are available and can be used to support the smooth running of match activities.

However, the capacity of available supporting facilities is still relatively limited. This can be seen especially in athletes' warmup rooms which often experience congestion, especially when the match schedule is busy. This condition causes some athletes to have to warm up in outdoor areas that are less representative and do not fully meet comfort and safety standards.

Limited space capacity also has the potential to affect the quality of athletes' preparation before competition, as well as can have an impact on performance and injury risk. Therefore, the existence of adequate supporting facilities, both in terms of quantity and quality, is an important factor in supporting the success of the match.

Figure 2. Venue POMNAS / Operator VAR (Video Assistant Referee)

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c. Security and Safety Facilities

Safety facilities for the implementation of pencak silat matches in the XIX National Student Sports Week (POMNAS) are generally available and support security during the activity. Safety facilities such as match mats, arena dividers, and evacuation routes have been provided according to the basic needs of organizing the match. The use of match mats that meet the standards also plays a role in minimizing the risk of injury to athletes during competition.

In addition, the presence of medical officers and security officers on standby during the match shows the organizers' attention to safety aspects and handling emergency conditions. This is one of the important factors in ensuring the safety of all parties involved, both athletes, officials, and spectators.

However, based on the results of observations, the direction of evacuation at several points in the building area has not been clearly seen. This condition has the potential to cause confusion for facility users in the event of an emergency situation, so that it can hinder the evacuation process. Therefore, the existence of a clear and easy-to-understand safety information system is very important in supporting match safety standards.

d. Cleanliness and Comfort

The cleanliness of the match arena and public facilities are quite good. The janitor cleans regularly. However, during the busy hours of the match, the area around the stands and the athletes' waiting room seemed to be less neatly organized due to the high activity of athletes and officials.

e. Accessibility and Mobility Flow

The flow of mobility of athletes, officials, and spectators has not been completely separated. On several occasions, it was seen that there was congestion at the entrance to the match arena, especially during the change of match sessions. This has the potential to disrupt the smooth operation and comfort of participants.

Summary of Key Findings

In general, the management of facilities and infrastructure in the implementation of POMNAS XIX pencak silat sports has been running quite well and supports the smooth running of the match. However, there are still some weaknesses in terms of supporting facility capacity, user mobility flow, and optimization of facility maintenance during busy activities. These findings show the need for more careful planning, strengthening coordination between committees, and adding supporting facilities for the implementation of large-scale sports events in the future.

IV. DISCUSSION

Based on the results of interviews and observations, the management of facilities and infrastructure in the implementation of POMNAS XIX pencak silat sports in general has run quite well and is able to support the smooth implementation of the match. This can be seen from the availability of main facilities such as the match arena, match mats, athletes' rooms, official rooms, as well as technical, medical, and security support during the activity.

However, from the planning aspect, there are still limitations in preparation time which has an impact on the suboptimal mapping of the needs of supporting facilities. Some supporting rooms such as the warm-up room, dressing room, and athlete waiting area are not fully adequate in terms of capacity. This condition shows that the planning stage of facilities and infrastructure needs to be carried out more systematically by referring to the analysis of needs based on the number of participants, the match schedule, and the characteristics of the pencak silat sport which requires a large enough space to move and warm.

In terms of organization and implementation, facility management has been carried out by a special team of facilities and infrastructure, but coordination between fields at the beginning of implementation has not been optimal. This can be seen from the delay in the distribution of equipment and the lack of organized mobility flow of athletes, officials, and spectators. In sports event management, cross-field coordination is the main key so that facilities and infrastructure can be used effectively and efficiently.

In terms of supervision and maintenance, the cleanliness and feasibility of facilities are relatively maintained during the activity. However, the limited number of technical and cleaning officers during crowded matches caused the response to minor damage or the rearrangement of facilities to be less fast. In addition, safety aspects such as evacuation directions are not fully visible, so it needs to receive more attention in organizing large-scale sports events.

The findings of this study are in line with the concept of sports facilities and infrastructure management which emphasizes the importance of careful planning, structured management, and continuous evaluation so that the available facilities are truly able to support the comfort, safety, and performance of athletes during the match.

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V. CONCLUSIONS

The management of facilities and infrastructure in the implementation of the XIX National Student Sports Week (POMNAS) of pencak silat sports in general has run quite well and is able to support the smooth implementation of the match. The main facilities of the match, such as courts, mats, and other supporting equipment are available in decent conditions and in accordance with standards so that they can ensure the safety and smooth running of the match.

However, there are still some obstacles to supporting facilities. Facilities such as warming rooms, dressing rooms, and athlete waiting areas are still limited in terms of capacity and comfort. This condition has the potential to affect athletes' readiness before competing and comfort during activities.

In addition, coordination between committees in the management of facilities and infrastructure as well as the regulation of the mobility flow of facility users has not been fully optimal. This is especially evident during the busy match schedule, where there is congestion at several points in the venue area, such as access in and out of athletes, officials, and spectators.

From the maintenance aspect, the match facilities in general have been well maintained. However, the limited number of technical and cleaning officers caused the management of facilities to not be optimal, especially in maintaining cleanliness and readiness of facilities during the match.

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